

CHARACTER, ABILITY, AND ACTION ARE THE QUALITIES OF THE UNITY OF HUMAN ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This study presents data based on the development of character, abilities and actions in psychology based on the state of human activity. Based on this data, instructions are given for diagnosing the state of psychological development of a person and eliminating psychological problems that arise in increasing the ability of human activity. In our psychological studies, all psychological changes related to human activity are shown with examples.*

Keywords: *Character, ability, psychological research, character problem, psychological characteristics, temperament, character trait.*

ХАРАКТЕР, СПОСОБНОСТЬ И ДЕЙСТВИЕ — КАЧЕСТВА ЕДИНСТВА ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В исследовании приводятся данные о состоянии развития человеческой деятельности в психологии, основанные на изучении характера, способностей и поведения. На основании этой информации даются указания по диагностике состояния психологического развития личности и устранению возникающих психологических проблем в повышении работоспособности человека. В этих психологических исследованиях все психологические изменения, связанные с деятельностью человека, иллюстрируются примерами.*

Ключевые слова: *Характер, способности, психологическое исследование, проблема характера, психологические характеристики, темперамент, черта характера.*

XARAKTER, QOBILIYAT VA HARAKAT INSON FAOLIYATINING BIRLIGI SIFATI

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqot psixologiyada xarakter, qobiliyat va harakatning inson faoliyatining rivojlanish holatidan kelib chiqqan holda asoslangan ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan. Bu ma'lumotlarga asoslangan holda shaxsning psixologik rivojlanish holatini diagnostika qilish va*

inson faoliyatining qobiliyatini oshirishdagi yuzaga keladigan psixologik muammolarni bartaraf etish bo'yicha ko'rsatmalar berib boriladi. Ushbu psixologik tadqiqotlarimizda inson faoliyatiga bog'liq barcha psixologik o'zgarishlar misollar bilan ko'rsatib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Xarakter, qobiliyat, psixologik tadqiqotlar, xarakter muammosi, psixologik xususiyatlar, temperament, xarakter xislati.*

Introduction

In psychological changes in each person, the concept of character and abilities is distinguished from any other person by his individual psychological characteristics. In this psychological process, the main attention is paid to the problem of character. The word "character" is derived from the Greek word and means "psychological sign". Any person living and working in social life is distinguished from other people by his individual psychological characteristics, and these differences are expressed in his character traits. Therefore, not all individual human characteristics can be included in the character trait. For example, individual psychological characteristics such as intelligence, memory stability, and visual acuity are examples of this. Despite the different definitions of character in the field of psychology, they are consistent in emphasizing its main features. For example, a person's behavior is characterized by a set of stable characteristics that are manifested in typical ways, activities, and relationships. A person's attitude towards society is his main sign. The main feature of psychological character is that it is always manifested in activity, in a person's attitude to the environment and people. When determining a person's character, it is not said that a person has shown courage, conscientiousness, sincerity, but that this person is a brave, honest, sincere person, that is, the characteristics of a person's character belong to the person himself. But not all characteristics can be considered inherent in a person, they must be significant and stable. Character is the unique basis, core of a person. Character, like focus, combines the most significant features of a person as a subject of activity, communication and knowledge. Character is formed throughout life and can change over time. Character can be expressed in the content and form of behavior, in the goals pursued by a person and the means or methods of its implementation. In its formation, development and task performance, human character is inextricably linked with temperament. In psychological research, four main points of view can be distinguished from the dominant ones regarding the relationship between character and temperament: the analogy of character and temperament (E. Krechmer, A. Ruzhitsky); the comparison of character and temperament, emphasizing the contrast between them (P. Viktorov, V. Virenius); the recognition of temperament as an element, essence, and unchanging part of character (S.L. Rubinstein, S.

Gorodetsky); the acceptance of temperament as the natural basis of character (L.S. Vygotsky, B.G. Anan'ev). A common feature for character and temperament is the dependence on the physiological characteristics of a person and, first of all, on the type of nervous system. Temperament determines such aspects of character as the proportionality or disproportion of behavior, the mobility or slowness of affect, etc. However, temperament does not determine character in advance. People with the same temperament characteristics can have completely different characters. Temperament characteristics can help or hinder the formation of certain aspects of character. As for the assumption that psychologists know everything about people, this is not an exaggeration. However, they can understand many situations faster and be more observant than ordinary people, because people who study psychology can be very observant compared to ordinary people. However, keep in mind that all thoughts are possible thoughts. If a psychologist says that I don't understand you very well, then this is not a real psychologist. A psychologist is a person who can quickly communicate with people and understand people. Each person is born with a certain set of abilities, but we learn this throughout our lives. We can feel that the states in people's behavior are innate, these can be individual behaviors. For example, the strength of the nervous system, behavior, etc. However, empathy in communication can be more difficult. Among psychologists, human behavior is different. However, a practical psychologist is required to have a number of skills. He must develop a tendency to communicate and the ability to understand people. There are psychological methods that are suitable for this. A psychologist is a person who can control the behavior, emotions, and thoughts of others and is specially trained for this. He can use specific techniques, for example, hypnosis. In fact, a practical psychologist can use certain methods of influencing people, but they do not engage in hypnosis, hypnosis is mainly used by medical workers, but psychologists use a number of methods to convince people, they can use the psychologist to ease the problems of gaining the client's trust. By character, we mean the individual characteristics that are formed in a person under the influence of environment and upbringing and are manifested in his willpower, his relationship to the world around him (other people, work, objects), and to himself. The characteristics that belong to the psychological character of a person are called character traits. Character traits are not accidental features that occur in a person, but are permanent, stable features of a person's behavior, and these features are unique to the person. Every person can sometimes show courage, strength, honesty, and sincerity. However, such features that occur only at certain times in a person's life and work cannot yet be his stable character traits. When we want to describe a person's character, we do not say that this person showed courage or showed honesty or sincerity, but rather that this person is brave, honest, and sincere. This word, courage, honesty, and sincerity,

is a word that refers to the virtues inherent in this person, his character traits, such that we can inevitably expect this person to show courage, honesty, and sincerity at the appropriate time. If we know the character traits of a person, we can correctly predict or say in advance what behavior this person will show at a given moment. Some of the traits that make up a person's character have historically emerged and changed depending on the development of social relations. In a class society, character also has class traits. The same trait in a person's character is evaluated differently in different social environments: a trait that is considered positive for one social class or historical period becomes negative for another class or social period. With the change in social relations, many character traits that are characteristic of a certain group or class are re-educated or disappear, while new character traits appear. The qualities of will that have become strong in a person and become his personal characteristic are the qualities of character related to will. Therefore, in the teaching of character, it is necessary to dwell again on the qualities of will, such as self-control, courage, and determination. But here we are not talking about their occasional appearance in a person, but about the fact that such qualities turn into personal qualities of a person, about their manifestation as certain character traits. Character traits of a person associated with will, as a rule, are manifested in a certain proportion with emotional characteristics in him. The will of some people prevails over feelings. Such people can immediately suppress any feelings that may interfere with achieving their goal. Usually, such people are called strong-willed, strong-willed people. There are also people whose behavior is dominated by emotions; such people often act under the influence of feelings that arise spontaneously in their actions. The emotions of such people are strong, they are easily influenced by random moods and feelings, therefore their character is described as emotional. In some people, volitional activity is manifested "psychologically" along with emotions. For example, hard work is a character trait. The psychological activity of labor requires a person to exert endurance and willpower, which is facilitated by a feeling of love for labor, which makes labor enjoyable. Such a ratio of will and emotions is a sign of a flawless, harmonious character. This trait of a person's character is especially evident in a complex situation that requires a quick, quick decision-making on one of several things or possibilities, and sometimes requires taking risks. Indecision, cowardice are negative character traits. An indecisive, cowardly person makes decisions very slowly, and often does not implement the decisions he makes on time. Such a person doubts the correctness of his decision when performing various possible, probable, and, especially, risky tasks. Stability is closely related to determination and is a positive character trait. People with this character trait usually do not change, cancel, or fail to fulfill their decisions. Such people are generous and keep their word; their words and deeds match each other. Such people are firm in their

word, they can be trusted and relied on. By unstable people we mean people who often change or waver in their decisions. Such people do not keep their word, they are unsubstantiated. Such people cannot be trusted or relied on.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we believe that information based on psychological research based on the development of character, abilities, and behavior in human activity can help in the psychological development of a person. Based on the psychological development of a person, it is necessary to diagnose the psychological development of a person and eliminate the psychological problems that arise in increasing the ability of a person to perform activities.

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